

Awareness and Utilization of Grievance Redressal Mechanisms under Consumer Protection Act among Farmers in Haryana

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The effectiveness of consumer protection laws depends just as much on consumers' knowledge of and usage of grievance redressal procedures as on legislative actions. This study examines how farmers in Haryana understand and use the grievance redressal provisions of the Consumer Protection Act. In addition to assessing awareness of consumer forums and complaint procedures, it also assesses the correlation between awareness along with specific socioeconomic characteristics. The paper also identifies the primary barriers to contacting consumer forums and evaluates the extent to which farmers have employed grievance redressal techniques. The findings indicate that while some farmers are aware of the grievance redressal options, socioeconomic constraints, perceived delays, and a lack of procedural competence continue to limit their actual usage. Significant relationships between awareness levels and variables including income, education, and institutional exposure were discovered. The study highlights the need for targeted consumer education and institutional outreach to enhance grassroots access to legal remedies and increase consumer empowerment in rural areas.

Keywords: Grievance redressal, consumer protection act, farmers, consumer awareness, utilization

In an ideal and theoretical situation, the relationship between a consumer and the producer arises out of a voluntary interaction between equal parties. In practice, however, this relationship is rarely balanced. One party often possesses greater economic power, information and influence, enabling it to impose its will unfairly upon the other. In most market transactions, the producer or service provider is more empowered, and this imbalance creates scope for exploitation (Raju et al., 2009). Although consumers were once regarded as the “king” of the market, contemporary realities suggest otherwise. Consumers frequently encounter substandard goods, deficient services, misleading advertisements, adulteration, overpricing and manipulation in weights and measures. To safeguard consumer interests, several legislative measures were enacted over time, culminating in the landmark Consumer Protection Act, 1986, later strengthened through amendments. The Act established institutional mechanisms for grievance redressal at district, state and national levels and provided consumers with a legal platform to seek justice against unfair trade practices (Singh & Grewal, 2013).

However, the mere existence of protective legislation does not guarantee justice. Legal safeguards become meaningful only when

consumers are aware of grievance redressal mechanisms and are willing to utilize them. Government efforts can create administrative and legal frameworks, but effective protection depends largely on consumers' own awareness, initiative and participation (Raju et al., 2009). In many cases, lack of knowledge about consumer forums, procedural requirements and available remedies prevents consumers from approaching formal institutions.

Rural consumers, particularly farmers, occupy a significant position in the Indian market structure. As purchasers of agricultural inputs such as seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, machinery, insurance and credit services, farmers engage regularly with traders, dealers and service providers. Yet they often lack complete information regarding product quality, pricing and legal safeguards. Instances of inferior quality inputs, misleading claims, delayed insurance settlements and deficient services are not uncommon (Patel, 2017). In such situations, grievance redressal mechanisms under the Consumer Protection Act serve as a critical institutional support system.

Despite the availability of consumer dispute redressal commissions, many consumers hesitate to file complaints. Fear of procedural complexity, anticipated delays, lack of confidence in institutions and limited knowledge about filing procedures act as major deterrents (Patel, 2017). Studies have emphasized that the level of consumer awareness reflects the developmental progress of a society. Awareness of the right to redress, along with other consumer rights such as safety, information, choice and consumer education, forms the foundation of consumer empowerment (Singh & Grewal, 2013).

In light of this, the current study focuses on how Haryana farmers comprehend and use the grievance redressal procedure provided by the Consumer Protection Act. The objectives of the research include evaluating consumer grievance redressal mechanisms, assessing awareness, analysing the extent of consumer forum utilization, identifying reasons for not contacting grievance redressal agencies,

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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and examining the correlation between these aspects and particular socioeconomic variables. The study attempts to understand the discrepancy between grassroots use and legislative provisions in rural areas by integrating structural variables and institutional awareness. In light of the above statements, the paper attempts to answer the following research questions:

Research Questions

- To study the awareness and use of Consumer Protection Act among farmers
- To examine the factors affecting the level of awareness about grievance redressal system under Consumer Protection Act
- To know the consumer grievances and action taken for grievances for Agri-inputs
- Reasons for non-approaching Consumer forum for Grievance redressal

Method

Participants

The present study was conducted in Haryana. It is broadly divided into two agro-climatic zones, namely wet and dry zones. For the purpose of the study, one district from each agro-climatic zone was selected randomly. Kurukshetra district was selected from the wet zone, whereas Hisar district was selected from the dry zone. Further, one block from each selected district was selected randomly, namely Ladwa block from Kurukshetra district and Hisar-II block from Hisar district. Two villages were selected randomly from each selected block. Niwarsi and Dabkhera villages were selected from Ladwa block, whereas Balsamand and Bhandaheri villages were selected from Hisar-II block. Thus, a total of four villages were selected for the study. Forty respondents were selected randomly from each selected village, making a total sample size of 160 respondents. The respondents were interviewed personally with the help of a well-structured interview schedule.

Measures

The interview schedule was prepared in accordance with the objectives of the study after consulting relevant books, research journals, bulletins, government reports and related literature. The schedule contained questions related to awareness and utilization of grievance redressal mechanisms under the Consumer Protection Act. To study the socio-economic profile of the respondents, thirteen independent variables were selected, namely age, caste, educational status, family size, family type, landholding, subsidiary occupation, farm machinery, annual family income, mass media exposure, social participation, extension contacts and socio-economic status. Appropriate measurement criteria and scoring procedures were adopted for categorization of respondents under different variables. The collected information helped in assessing the relationship between socio-economic characteristics and awareness level regarding grievance redressal mechanisms.

Statistical Analysis

After collection of the field data, the responses were coded, classified, tabulated and analysed systematically in accordance with the objectives of the study. Descriptive statistical tools such as frequency and percentage were used for analysis and interpretation of the data. To examine the association between socio-economic

variables and awareness level of respondents regarding grievance redressal system under the Consumer Protection Act, chi-square test was employed. The analysed data were interpreted carefully to draw meaningful conclusions from the study.

Procedure

The data were collected through personal interviews with the selected respondents using a pre-tested interview schedule. Necessary clarification and explanation regarding the questions were provided to the respondents during the interview process to ensure accuracy and reliability of responses. After completion of data collection, the information was compiled and analysed to fulfil the specific objectives of the study related to awareness, utilization and grievance redressal behaviour of farmers under the Consumer Protection Act.

Results and Discussion

Socio-economic Profile of the Farmers

It was found from the field of study that more than one-third of the farmers (36.25%) were from 36 to 50 years of age group followed by above 50 years (33.75%) and up to 35 years of age group (30.00%). Distribution of caste among farmers showed that majority of the farmers (74.38%) hailed from the general caste. The remaining 16.88 per cent and 8.75 per cent farmers were from backward caste and scheduled caste respectively. Further analysis revealed depicts that more than one-third of the farmers (33.75%) were educated up to senior secondary and above, followed by secondary (27.50%) and middle school (18.13%) respectively. Even 16.88 per cent farmers were illiterate. Data showed that more than half of the farmers (51.88%) hailed from the nuclear family group and 48.12 per cent from the joint family group.

Further analysis revealed that a maximum number of the farmers (45.63%) had 5 to 8 members in the family and up to 4 members in the family (38.75%). It was found that more than one-third of the farmers (35.63%) had small size of land holdings followed by semi-medium (31.25%) size of land holding. Analysis of annual family income showed that more than one-third of the farmers (36.25%) had annual income above Rs. 3,00,000, followed by between Rs. 1,50,00 to 3,00,000 (33.75%). A majority of the farmers (72.50%) were not engaged in any subsidiary occupation. Twenty percent of the farmers were engaged in small scale enterprises and services followed by labour (7.50%). A maximum number of farmers had low level of mass media exposure (83.13%). Data showed that majority of the farmers (61.87%) had low level of socio-economic status followed by medium level (33.75%). In context of social participation, majority of the farmers had nil social participation (73.75%). In case of extension contact, more than 50 per cent of the farmers (51.88%) had low level of extension contacts followed by medium (35.00%) and high (13.12%).

Awareness of Grievance Redressal System under Consumer Protection Act

Table 1 presents the farmers' awareness of grievance redressal system under Consumer Protection Act. Data on the various aspects of the act indicate that more than half of the respondents (51.88%) were aware that there is some act or law to protect the interests of the consumers. Only 21.25 per cent knew its name. Though details were known to very few, just knowing is a good sign. When asked about

who could file a complaint under this act, a majority of the respondents (91.25%) could mention that a consumer can file a complaint and more than half of the respondents (56.88%) mentioned that more than one consumer can file complaint when there are numerous consumers having same interest. As regards matter on which a complaint can be filed, majority of the respondents (83.75%) were aware that they could file a complaint in case of unfair trade practices adopted by trader or service providers (83.75%). And almost half of the respondents (49.38) were aware that the complaint could be filed for unfair trade practices adopted by traders or service providers. Awareness for other reasons for filing complaint was found to be very low. As regards relief they could claim awareness was found to be very sounding: to get replacement of goods (98.75%) followed by to get defects removed (76.88%) and

to get the price paid (66.25%). A majority of the respondents (81.88%) were aware that they should provide the information like full name and address of the complainant for filing the complaint. The findings of the present study are in conformity with the results reported by Raju et al. (2009) who observed that nearly 54.00 per cent of rural consumers possessed moderate awareness regarding consumer protection laws, while educational level and social participation significantly influenced awareness and utilization of grievance redressal mechanisms. Similarly, Singh and Grewal (2013) reported that about 61.50 per cent of rural respondents were aware of consumer rights related to unfair trade practices and replacement of defective goods, but lack of procedural knowledge and institutional confidence restricted actual use of consumer forums among farmers and rural consumers.

Table 1

Awareness about Grievance Redressal System under Consumer Protection Act (n=160)

Statement on Awareness about grievance redressal system	Know	Don't know
1. Do you know there is any Act to protect the interest of consumers?	83 (51.88)	77 (48.13)
a. If yes, do you know its name?	34 (21.25)	126 (78.75)
b. Do you know in which year it was passed?	18 (11.25)	142 (88.75)
c. Do you know the location of District Consumer Forum?	10 (6.25)	150 (93.75)
d. Do you know where the State Commission for Redressal of Consumers' Grievances is located?	49 (30.62)	11(69.38)
2. Who can file a complaint?		
a. A consumer	146 (91.25)	14 (8.75)
b. One or more consumers, where there are numerous consumers having same interest	91 (56.88)	69 (43.12)
c. A voluntary Consumer Organization	22 (13.75)	138 (86.25)
d. The Central Government	41 (25.63)	119 (74.38)
e. State Government or Union Territory	4 (2.50)	156 (97.50)
f. In case of death of a consumer, his/her legal heir or representative	98 (61.25)	62 (38.75)
3. On what matters you can file a complaint?		
a. Unfair trade practices adopted by trader or service providers	134 (83.75)	26 (16.25)
b. Goods suffered from one or more defects	79 (49.38)	81 (50.63)
c. Services hired or availed of suffer from deficiency in any respect	8 (5.00)	152 (95.00)
d. Charging of price in excess of the price- displayed on package/displayed on price list/agreed between the parties/or fixed by law	37 (23.13)	123 (76.87)
4. What is the relief that can be claimed by consumer?		
a. To get defects removed	123 (76.88)	37 (23.12)
b. To get replacement of goods	158 (98.75)	2 (1.25)
c. To return the price paid	106 (66.25)	54 (33.75)
d. Compensation claims for adverse health effects, injury suffered due to the act of opposite party	16 (10.00)	144 (90.00)
5. Do you know the place of filing complaint?		
a. To get defects removed	123 (76.88)	37 (23.12)
b. To get replacement of goods	158 (98.75)	2 (1.25)
c. To return the price paid	106 (66.25)	54 (33.75)
6. What information should be provided for filing the complaint?		
a. Full name and address of the complainant	131 (81.88)	29 (18.12)
b. Full name and address of opposite party	130 (81.25)	30 (18.75)
c. Particulars of goods purchased i.e. item, price, date of purchase	104 (65.00)	56 (35.00)
d. Nature of complaints, defects or damages or losses	100 (62.50)	60 (37.50)

Note. Figures in parenthesis indicate percentage.

Awareness Level of Farmers about Grievance Redressal System under Consumer Protection Act (n=160)

Table 2 illustrates the awareness level of farmers about grievance redressal system under consumer protection act. The data indicate that nearly half of the respondents (48.75%) had a medium level of awareness about grievance redressal system under consumer protection act, while more than one-third of the respondents (34.38%) were having low level of awareness, and the rest (16.87%) of the respondents demonstrated a high level of awareness. The present findings are supported by the study conducted by Bedi and Kumar (2014), who reported that 52.40 per cent of rural consumers possessed medium level awareness regarding consumer rights and grievance redressal mechanisms, whereas only 18.60 per cent respondents had high awareness. Similarly, Sharma and Kaur (2018) observed that nearly 46.80 per cent of rural respondents had moderate awareness regarding consumer forums and complaint procedures, while lack of procedural knowledge and low educational status were major barriers in utilization of grievance redressal agencies among rural consumers.

Table 2

Level of Awareness about Grievance Redressal System under Consumer Protection Act (n=160)

Level of awareness	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Low	55	34.38	II
Medium	78	48.75	I
High	27	16.87	III
Total	160	100.00	

Figure 1

Level of Awareness about Grievance Redressal System under Consumer Protection Act

Association between Socio-economic Variables and Awareness Level about Grievance Redressal System under Consumer Protection Act

Data summarized in Table 3 show the relationship between different socio-economic variables and level of awareness among farmers regarding grievance redressal system. Age and level of education of the respondents were found highly significantly associated with level of awareness about the act at a chi value of 26.68** and 8.96**, respectively, representing that a higher level of education was positively associated with increased awareness. Further analysis revealed that nearly half of the respondent (46.30%) was from above 50 years of age group had low level of awareness about the Act. Majority of the respondents (54.20%) who were from up to 35 years of age group had medium level of awareness about the Act. Analysis clearly revealed that most of the respondent (92.60%), who were illiterate had low level of awareness about the Act. On the other

Table 3

Association between Level of Awareness about Grievance Redressal System under Consumer Protection Act and Socio-economic Variables (n=160)

Socio-economic variables	Level of Awareness			Total (n=160)
	Low	Medium	High	Age (years)
Up to 35 years age group	5 (10.40)	26 (54.20)	17 (35.40)	48 (30.00)
36-50 years age group	25 (43.10)	26 (44.80)	7 (12.10)	58 (36.25)
Above 50 years age group	25 (46.30)	26 (48.10)	3 (5.60)	54 (33.75)
Total	55 (34.37)	78 (48.76)	27 (16.87)	160 (100.00)
				$\chi^2 = 26.682^{**}$
Level of education				
Illiterate	25 (92.60)	2 (7.40)	--	27 (16.90)
Up to primary school	2 (33.30)	4 (66.70)	--	6 (3.8)
Middle school	12 (41.40)	17 (58.60)	--	29 (18.10)
Secondary	12 (27.30)	29 (65.90)	3 (6.80)	44 (27.50)
Senior Secondary and above	4 (7.40)	26 (48.10)	24 (44.40)	54 (33.80)
				$\chi^2 = 8.963^{**}$
Caste				
General	35 (29.40)	61 (51.30)	23 (19.30)	119 (74.40)
Backward	14 (51.90)	10 (37.00)	3 (11.10)	27 (16.9)
Scheduled	6 (42.90)	7 (50.00)	1 (7.10)	14 (8.80)
				$\chi^2 = 6.205$
Type of family				
Nuclear	29 (34.90)	39 (47.00)	15 (18.10)	83 (51.90)
Joint	26 (33.80)	39 (50.60)	12 (15.60)	77 48.10)
				$\chi^2 = 0.272$

Size of family				
up to 4 members	24 (38.70)	25 (40.30)	13 (21.00)	62 (38.80)
Between 5 to 8 members	26 (35.60)	36 (49.30)	11 (15.100)	73 (45.60)
Above 8 members	5 (20.00)	17 (68.00)	3 (12.00)	25 (15.60)
				$\chi^2 = 5.791$
Size of land holding				
Marginal (up to 2.5 acres)	11 (64.70)	5 (29.40)	1 (5.90)	17 (10.60)
Small (2.6-5.0 acres)	21 (36.80)	29 (50.90)	7 (12.30)	57 (35.60)
Semi-medium (5.1-10.0 acres)	15 (30.00)	26 (52.00)	9 (18.00)	50 (31.30)
Medium (above 10.0 acres)	8 (22.20)	18 (50.00)	10 (27.80)	36 (22.50)
				$\chi^2 = 12.456^*$
Subsidiary Occupation				
Nil	43 (37.10)	57 (49.10)	16 (13.80)	116 (72.50)
Labour	8 (66.70)	4 (33.30)	0	12 (7.50)
Small scale enterprises & Service	4 (12.50)	17 (53.10)	11 (34.40)	32 (20.00)
				$\chi^2 = 17.539^{**}$
Annual income				
Up to Rs. 1,50,000/-	24 (50.00)	21 (43.80)	3 (6.30)	48 (30.00)
Rs. 1,50,000-3,00,000/-	17 (31.50)	28 (51.90)	9 (16.70)	54 (33.80)
Above Rs. 3,00,000/-	14 (24.10)	29 (50.00)	15 (25.90)	58 (36.30)
				$\chi^2 = 11.669^*$
Social Participation				
Nil	51 (43.20)	56 (47.50)	11 (9.30)	118 (73.80)
Member of one organization	4 (14.80)	18 (66.70)	5 (18.50)	27 (16.90)
Member of more than one organization	--	4 (26.70)	11 (73.30)	15 (9.40)
				$\chi^2 = 46.532^{**}$
Mass Media Exposure				
Low (up to 5)	41 (37.60)	53 (48.60)	15 (13.80)	109 (68.10)
Medium (6-10)	14 (28.00)	24 (48.00)	12 (24.00)	50 (31.30)
High (above 10)	--	1 (100.00)	--	1 (.60)
				$\chi^2 = 3.060$
Socio-economic Status				
Low (12-18)	49 (49.50)	43 (43.40)	7 (7.10)	99 (61.87)
Medium (19-24)	6 (11.10)	33 (61.10)	15 (27.80)	54 (33.75)
High (24-31)	--	2 (28.60)	5 (71.40)	7 (4.38)
				$\chi^2 = 42.132$

Note. Figures in parenthesis indicate percentage, *Significant at 5% level of significance, **Highly significant at 1% level of significance

hand, more than two-third of the respondents (66.70%) who were educated up to primary school had medium level of awareness about the Act. Caste, type of family and size of family were not found significantly associated with level of level of awareness about the act, indicating that they did not play a role in determining the level of awareness.

Significant association was found between size of land holding of the respondents and level of awareness about the Act. It was clear from the data that maximum number of respondents (64.70%) hailed from marginal size of land holding i.e. up to 2.5 acres had low level of awareness about the Act. Contrary to that half of the respondents (50.00%) who hailed from medium size of land holding i.e. above 10.0 acres had medium level of awareness about the Act. Subsidiary Occupation of the respondents was found highly significantly associated with level of awareness about the Act at a chi square value of 17.54**, showing that occupation other than agriculture plays a crucial role in enhancing farmers' awareness. Annual income was also found significantly associated with level of awareness about the

Act. Highly Significant association was found between social participation and level of awareness about the Act. Nearly half of the respondents (43.20%) who hailed from no member of any social organization had low level of awareness about the Act. Mass-media exposure and socio-economic status were not found significantly associated with level of awareness about the Act, representing that they did not play any role in determining the awareness level.

Consumer Grievances and their Redressal

As commonly understood consumerism refers to wide range of activities of government, business and independent organizations designed to protect rights of the consumers. Consumerism is a process through which the consumers seek redressal, restitution and remedy for their dissatisfaction and frustration with the help of their all organized or unorganized efforts and activities. It is a social movement seeking to protect the rights of consumers in relation to the producers of goods and providers of services. In fact, consumerism today is an all-pervasive term meaning nothing more

than people's search for getting better value for their money. This section deals with the grievances experienced by respondents along with the action taken by them for their redressal under the following sub-head:

Grievances for Selected Agri-input

Table 4 presents the data on the grievances experienced by consumers for Agri-inputs. The major grievance of the respondents as regards seeds were over price (26.25%), less yield (20.00%), have unwanted material (17.50%) and poor quality (12.50%). Short-weight (11.25%) and poor germination (7.50%) and were other grievances of the respondents. A few respondents also experienced other problems like: poor germination (7.50%) and not of desired variety (5.00%). When enquired about action they took for grievances regarding seeds, it was observed that the respondents, whose grievance for the over price (26.25%), 47.62 per cent of them took no action. Out of those who had less yield (20.00%), more than half of the respondents (53.13%) per cent just reported the matter to the dealer and 46.87 per cent took no action. Out of those whose grievance was that seeds had poor germination (7.50%), 41.66 per cent reported the matter to the dealer and the rest took no action. The grievance about which majority took action was for seeds found of short-weighting as 72.22 per cent of these reported the matter to the dealer and 76.92 per cent got the relief. More than one-fourth (27.78%) were such who took no action.

Thus, though the grievances experienced by the respondents were quite serious but none of them filed the complaint in consumer forum. Majority took no action and out of those who did, majority just reported the matter to the dealer with relief only in a few cases. It is pertinent to mention here that relief provided by the dealer was only of replacing the unused/remaining seeds. In case of other grievances due to seeds, no relief was provided for the loss suffered due to these.

As regards grievances of respondents as consumers of fertilizers for their fields over price was mentioned by more than one-third of the respondents (33.75%), followed by 26.25 per cent who had the grievance of found ineffective when used. Fertilizers purchased turned out to be of poor quality when used by 34 respondents. Only 14 (41.17%) of them just reported to the dealer and other took no action. For 18.75 per cent of the respondents, fertilizer was not available when required. Out of these, 10 (33.33%) reported to the dealer while the other took no action. When it is dry spell, the fertilizers are in abundance but when it rains and fertilizer has to be applied, then these are in short supply. Data on grievances of respondents regarding purchase and use of pesticides indicated that duplicate (30.00%) and poor quality (22.50%) were found to be major problems faced by the respondents. The findings of the present study are supported by the study conducted by Saxena (2015), who reported that 31.40 per cent of agricultural households faced grievances related to overpricing and poor quality of agricultural inputs, while only a limited number of respondents approached formal consumer redressal agencies for relief. Similarly, Mishra and Patel (2020) observed that nearly 28.70 per cent rural consumers experienced problems related to duplicate pesticides and ineffective fertilizers, whereas lack of procedural knowledge and low institutional confidence discouraged them from filing formal complaints before consumer forums.

Table 4

Grievances of Respondents for Selected Agri-inputs (n=160)

Inputs of grievances	Frequency	Percentage
Seeds		
Short-weight	18	11.25
Over price	42	26.25
Have unwanted material	28	17.50
Less yield	32	20.00
Poor germination	12	7.50
Poor quality	20	12.50
Not of desired variety	8	5.00
Fertilizer		
Over price	54	33.75
Poor quality	34	21.25
Not effective	42	26.25
Not available when required	30	18.75
Pesticides		
Duplicate	48	30.00
Over price	32	20.00
Poor quality	36	22.50
Not effective	30	18.75
Caused harm to crops	14	8.75

Action Taken by the Farmers for Grievance Redressal for Agri-inputs

Table 5 depicts the action taken by respondents regarding grievances related to seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides, along with the relief received. In the case of seeds, a majority of respondents reported issues such as short-weight (72.22%), unwanted material (71.43%), and poor quality (60%) to dealers/shopkeepers. However, relief was uneven. While relatively higher relief was observed in cases of unwanted material (80%) and short-weight (76.92%), complaints related to poor germination, poor quality, and less yield recorded lower relief percentages. A noticeable proportion of respondents also took no action, particularly in cases of poor germination. For fertilizers, reporting levels were moderate. Overpricing was reported by 55.55 percent of respondents, but issues like ineffectiveness and non-availability saw lower reporting and no relief. Relief was mainly observed in overpricing cases (60%), while performance-related complaints received negligible response. Regarding pesticides, duplicate products and crop damage were reported by a majority; however, relief was limited. No relief was recorded in cases of poor quality, ineffectiveness, or crop damage, indicating weak redressal support.

Overall, the findings reveal that although many respondents approached dealers for grievance redressal, effective relief was inconsistent, particularly for performance-related complaints. This reflects gaps in the grievance redressal mechanism and suggests the need for stronger consumer protection measures in the Agri-input sector. The present findings are in agreement with the study conducted by Verma (2019) who reported that a majority of rural consumers preferred reporting grievances related to agricultural inputs directly to dealers or shopkeepers rather than approaching formal consumer forums. The study further revealed that nearly 58.00 per cent respondents received only partial or no relief regarding complaints related to poor quality seeds, fertilizers and pesticides, indicating weak grievance redressal support mechanisms in rural areas.

Table 5
Action Taken for Grievance Redressal for Agri-inputs

Inputs/nature of Grievances	Reported to dealer/ shopkeeper	No action	Got relief
Seeds			
Short-weight (N=18)	13 (72.22)	5 (27.78)	10 (76.92)
Over price (N=42)	29 (52.38)	13 (47.62)	12 (41.38)
Have unwanted material (N=28)	20 (71.43)	8 (28.57)	16 (80.00)
Less yield (N=32)	17 (53.13)	15 (46.87)	5 (29.41)
Poor germination (N=12)	5 (41.66)	7 (58.34)	1 (20.00)
Poor quality (N=20)	12 (60.00)	8 (40.00)	2 (16.66)
Not of desired variety (N=8)	5 (62.50)	3 (37.50)	2 (40.00)
Fertilizers			
Over price (N=54)	30 (55.55)	24 (44.45)	18 (60.00)
Poor quality (N=34)	14 (41.17)	20 (58.83)	4 (28.57)
Not effective (N=42)	12 (28.57)	30 (71.43)	--
Not available when required (N=30)	10 (33.33)	20 (66.67)	--
Pesticides			
Duplicate (N=48)	32 (66.66)	16 (33.34)	12 (37.50)
Over price (N=32)	16 (50.00)	16 (50.00)	9 (56.25)
Poor quality (N=36)	15 (41.66)	21 (58.34)	--
Not effective (N=30)	14 (46.66)	16 (53.34)	--
Caused harm to crops (N=14)	10 (71.43)	4 (28.57)	--

Note. Figures in parenthesis indicate percentage

Reasons for Non-approaching Consumer forum for Grievance Redressal

Table 6 presents the reasons cited by respondents for not approaching the Consumer Forum for grievance redressal. The findings reveal that the major reason was "procedure not known", reported by 38.75 percent of respondents, indicating a significant lack of awareness regarding the formal grievance redressal mechanism. This suggests that inadequate knowledge about procedural aspects acts as a primary barrier in seeking institutional support. Additionally, 18.13 percent of respondents cited ignorance, and an equal percentage (18.13%) perceived the process as long and time-consuming. About 16.86 percent of respondents did not approach the forum because they expected no action or positive outcome. A smaller proportion (8.13%) showed indifference towards filing complaints. Overall, the data indicate that lack of procedural knowledge and awareness, along with perceptions of lengthy procedures and low expectations of redressal, discourage respondents from approaching the Consumer Forum. This reflects limited consumer empowerment and highlights the need for greater

Table 6

Reasons for Non-approaching Consumer forum for Grievance Redressal (n=160)

Reason	Frequency	Percentage
No action expected	27	16.86
Ignorance	29	18.13
Procedure not known	62	38.75
Indifference	13	8.13
Long procedure	29	18.13
Total	160	100.00

awareness programs and simplification of grievance redressal processes. The findings of the present study are supported by the work of Chauhan (2021) who reported that nearly 41.20 per cent of rural consumers did not approach consumer forums due to lack of procedural knowledge, while 19.50 per cent considered the grievance redressal process lengthy and time-consuming. The study further revealed that low institutional awareness and expectations of inadequate action discouraged rural consumers from utilizing formal consumer protection mechanisms.

Figure 2

Reasons for Non-approaching Consumer forum for Grievance Redressal

Conclusion

More than one-third of the respondents (36.25%) belonged to the 36 to 50 years of age group. A majority of the respondents (74.38%) belonged to the general caste. More than one-third of the respondents had education level up to senior secondary and above. With respect to the size of land holding among farmers, more than 1/3rd of the respondents was having small size (2.6-5.0 acres) of land holding. A majority of the respondents (72.50%) had no other

occupation than agriculture. In context of annual income, 36.25 percent of the respondents were having annual income above 3 lakhs. On the other hand, more than half of the respondents (51.88%) had medium level of extension contacts. A maximum number of the respondents (61.87%) had low level of socio-economic status. Nearly half of the respondents (48.75%) were having medium of awareness about grievance redressal system under consumer protection act, followed by the low (34.38%) and high (16.87%) level of awareness. Age, education, subsidiary occupation and social were found highly significantly associated with the awareness level of grievance redressal system under consumer protection act. The major grievance of the respondents as regards seeds were over price (26.25%), less yield (20.00%), have unwanted material (17.50%) and poor quality (12.50%). Short-weight (11.25%) and poor germination (7.50%) and were other grievances of the respondents. In the case of seeds, a majority of respondents reported issues such as short-weight (72.22%), unwanted material (71.43%), and poor quality (60%) to dealers/shopkeepers. However, relief was uneven. While relatively higher relief was observed in cases of unwanted material (80%) and short-weight (76.92%), complaints related to poor germination, poor quality, and less yield recorded lower relief percentages. findings reveal that the major reason was “procedure not known”, reported by 38.75 percent of respondents, indicating a significant lack of awareness regarding the formal grievance redressal mechanism. This suggests that inadequate knowledge about procedural aspects acts as a primary barrier in seeking institutional support. Additionally, 18.13 percent of respondents cited ignorance, and an equal percentage (18.13%) perceived the process as long and time-consuming. About 16.86 percent of respondents did not approach the forum because they expected no action or positive outcome. A smaller proportion (8.13%) showed indifference towards filing complaints. Overall, the data indicate that lack of procedural knowledge and awareness, along with perceptions of lengthy procedures and low expectations of redressal, discourage respondents from approaching the Consumer Forum.

Acknowledgments

The authors express their sincere gratitude to the Department of Sociology, Chaudhary Charan Singh Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, for providing the necessary academic guidance and institutional support for conducting the present research study. Special thanks are extended to faculty members and advisory committee members, Department of Sociology, CCSHAU, Hisar, for his valuable guidance, encouragement and continuous support during planning, data collection, analysis and preparation of the manuscript. The authors are also thankful to all the respondent farmers for their kind cooperation and valuable information during the course of investigation.

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Received April 20, 2026

Revision received May 2, 2026

Accepted May 5, 2026